

KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

KUMASI - GHANA

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SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AND DENTISTRY

DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNITY HEALTH

**THE PERSPECTIVE OF VOLUNTARY COUNSELLING AND TESTING FOR
HIV/AIDS IN SOME SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS IN ASUOGYAMAN DISTRICT**

BY

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**THE PERSPECTIVE OF VOLUNTARY COUNSELLING AND TESTING FOR
HIV/AIDS IN SOME SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS IN ASUOGYAMAN DISTRICT,
EASTERN REGION, GHANA.**

**A DISSERTATION PRESENTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNITY
HEALTH, SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AND DENTISTRY, KWAME NKRUMAH
UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, KUMASI, GHANA IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF MB. ChB DEGREE**

BY

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DECLARATION

DECLARATION

I, **FITZGERALD ADJIERTEH ADJETEY**, hereby declare that aside other investigations which have been duly cited and acknowledged, this dissertation was composed by myself, been solely the result of my own original work and supervised by my academic supervisor, Dr. Peter Twum and that this dissertation has not been submitted for any degree or professional qualification in any other institution.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my parents (Mr. and Mrs. Adjetey) and my siblings (Laud and Israel). I am grateful for their love and support.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am grateful to the Almighty God for seeing me through this project and my experience medical school. My sincerest gratitude also goes to my project supervisor, Dr. Peter Twum, whose advice and insight have been invaluable during this project. I would also want to express my gratitude to my parents, Mr. and Mrs. Adjetey, for their love, guidance and counselling during this project and my academic journey. I am deeply grateful and it is my prayer that God richly blesses you.

I would also like to thank Dr. John Ekow Otoo, the Deputy Regional Director of Public Health for the Eastern Regional Health Directorate of Ghana, Nana Boafo Ansaprem IV, the chief of Akosombo, Mrs. Rebecca Bantey, the Asuogyaman District Health Director, Madam Fatiha Osman the Headmistress of Akosombo International School, Mr. Anim Addo the headmaster of Akwamuman Senior High School and the students who participated in the study.

I am thankful to everyone else who assisted me during my district posting including my friends, group members, as well as acquaintances made during this period.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

HIVAIDS: Human Immunodeficiency Virus/ Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome

HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

VCT: Voluntary Counselling and Testing

SHS: Senior High School

WHO: World Health Organization

UN: United Nations

UNAIDS: United Nations Program on HIV/AIDS

PLWHIV: People living with HIV

PLWHA: People living with HIV/AIDS

ER: Emergency Room

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: HIV/AIDS is a significant global health problem and VCT is a major tool which can help foster early detection and prevent the spread. This study was conducted to examine the perspectives of senior high school students in the Asuogyaman District towards voluntary counselling and testing of HIV. The study involved a cross-sectional study of 250 adolescents aged 15 to 19 years.

METHODS AND RESULTS: A cross-sectional survey was conducted with 250 participants. Participants were senior high students in the Asuogyaman district who were aged 15 to 19 years. A structured questionnaire made up 30 items was used to collect data and processed using SPSS.

The results showed that a 71.2% of participants believed that getting tested for HIV was important but only a very small portion (3.2%) of students had received an HIV test. Most students admitted to some factors which influence the use of VCT which included fear of stigma and discrimination, lack of privacy at test centers and little encourage from friends and family.

CONCLUSION: It was recommended that there should be enhanced awareness campaigns on VCT, improve visibility and accessibility of test centers and institute community and family engagement programs to foster a supportive environment for VCT.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY:

HIV/AIDS continues to be a significant health concern globally, especially as it affects millions of people worldwide. In recent years, the prevalence of HIV/AIDS among young populations, including senior high school students, (Anaba, Buabeng and Okai, 2022) has raised alarm, especially as half of new infections are seen in young people.

An estimated number of 39 million people were found to be living with HIV globally in 2022 and 1.3 million new infections were recorded. (UNAIDS, 2022) The region most affected is Sub-Saharan Africa with 75% of new infections and 75% global deaths. The prevalence of HIV infection in Ghana was 1.7% in 2019 which translates to 334,713 people.(Ghana Aids Commission, 2019)

A pivotal measure in the fight against HIV/AIDS is knowing one's status. As such, in June 2021, United Nations member states adopted the 95-95-95 target was established by the Joint United Nations Program on HIV/AIDS to be attained by 2025.(Frescura *et al.*, 2022) That is, by 2025, 95% of people living with HIV (PLHIV) should know their status, 95% of those diagnosed with HIV should be on antiretroviral therapy and 95% of those on antiretroviral therapy should have a suppressed viral load.(Frescura *et al.*, 2022) In order to achieve this goal, early detection through voluntary testing is crucial.

The uneven distribution of HIV/AIDS awareness and its prevalence in various countries can be attributed to factors such as differences in healthcare facilities, cultural norms, and socioeconomic disparities.(Nkambule *et al.*, 2023) As a result, the environment in which seniors in high school deal with HIV/AIDS awareness and testing is complex and multidimensional. Comprehending these regional subtleties is crucial in order to customize interventions that effectively address the unique obstacles encountered by high school students across various environments.

Senior high schools are characterized by a dynamic social structure and the developmental stage of adolescence, further complicates the landscape. Adolescents are exposed to differing degrees of sexual education while navigating the intricacies of relationships, identity, and peer pressure. This period of development is critical for forming attitudes and actions, particularly those connected to VCT.

Furthermore, the stigma attached to HIV/AIDS is still a major obstacle that affects people's willingness to get tested and get counselling. Teenagers, who are frequently acutely aware of how society views them, may feel more stigma, which prevents them from having candid conversations and acting proactively to seek health care. Other obstacles they face include lack of awareness, concerns about privacy, low risk perceptions and poor knowledge of HIV/AIDS. (Idele *et al.*, 2014) Understanding senior high school students' perceptions on VCT necessitates a comprehensive examination of the backdrop of stigma in the high school setting.

Schools are crucial in forming the sociocultural dynamics of teenagers. Integrated comprehensive sexual education, awareness programs, and focused interventions can all be

implemented in educational settings. However, a full grasp of the current viewpoints, knowledge gaps, and obstacles to voluntary counselling and HIV/AIDS testing among senior high school students is necessary for such initiatives to be effective.

The study of senior high school students' perspectives on VCT stands out as a crucial investigation against this complicated background. This study intends to provide nuanced insights that can inform customized interventions, raise awareness, and create a supportive environment for high school students in their engagement with HIV/AIDS prevention and testing practices by examining the attitudes, knowledge levels, and contextual factors influencing voluntary counselling and testing.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The senior high school years is a pivotal period in the lives of adolescents. This is the period during which significant changes with regards to their physical, mental and social wellbeing occurs. They make decisions that affect their futures and these include decisions with regards to their sexual behaviors. A report by (UNICEF, 2023) showed about 140000 adolescents were newly infected with HIV. The report also showed testing rates were very low in Africa, especially West and Central Africa.

In the larger context of HIV/AIDS prevention, high school students play a crucial role, and their viewpoints on VCT are essential to developing successful public health initiatives. The role of VCT in HIV prevention through its prevention, treatment and support strategies cannot be overemphasized. VCT is essential for encouraging safe sex practices, offering support and creating a window of opportunity for early detection of HIV. (Pikard, 2009)

The voluntary counselling and testing (VCT) for HIV/AIDS among senior high school students stands out in the landscape of adolescent health as an important but understudied topic that need concentrated attention. Despite the abundance of research on HIV/AIDS prevalence, testing, and prevention, little is known about senior high school students' unique viewpoints on voluntary counselling and testing. Although a few existing studies like (Andoh-Robertson and Ofori, 2018) and (Djan, 2018) exist. Given this demographics' susceptibility to HIV/AIDS risks and the potential influence of early identification on prevention and intervention efforts, this knowledge gap is crucial since it makes it more difficult to create focused treatments and educational programs that are suited to the requirements of this population. Our comprehension of the elements impacting this population's attitudes, knowledge, and behaviors towards volunteer counselling and testing is limited by the lack of thorough research that focuses only on this demographic.

A significant deficiency in current understanding is the scant focus on the sociocultural factors affecting high school students' VCT viewpoints. The sociocultural factors affecting high school students' VCT viewpoints and the special opportunities and challenges that the high school environment presents, such as peer pressure, academic environments, and socioeconomic circumstances, which may have a substantial impact on students' views towards volunteer counselling and testing, deserve to be explored in the literature.

Also, studying the effectiveness of the present HIV/AIDS awareness programs in high schools is crucial to identify and understand the factors which influence the adolescents' uptake of voluntary counselling and testing of HIV. The differing effects of various intervention strategies should be sufficiently explored in various research studies, in order to bring educators and

policymakers to light about the best strategies to use when addressing the unique requirements of senior high school students.

Moreover, although certain research discusses the broad elements impacting teenage HIV testing habits, it frequently lacks detail about the viewpoints and experiences of high school students. The complex relationship between gender, academic standing, and socioeconomic background and how it shapes senior high school students' attitudes towards virtual and cognitive technologies (VCT) calls for a more in-depth investigation than has been done in the past.

By exploring the viewpoints of senior high school students on voluntary counselling and HIV/AIDS testing, this study seeks to close this important gap. This study aims to provide a basis for the creation of customized interventions, educational programs, and policies that speak to the unique needs and concerns of this population by assessing their attitudes, knowledge gaps, and potential hurdles. In the end, closing this information gap is essential to achieving the more general objectives of HIV/AIDS education and prevention among high school students as well as to develop a generation of people who make educated decisions and take an active role in their health.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- a) To assess the level of awareness and knowledge about HIV/AIDS and VCT among senior high school students.
- b) To identify the attitudes and perceptions of senior high school students towards VCT services.

c) To explore the factors and barriers that influence the decision-making process regarding the utilization of VCT utilization among senior high school students.

1.4 STUDY OBJECTIVES:

1.4.1 Main Objective:

The main objective of this study is to investigate the perspective of senior high school students with regards to voluntary counselling and testing for HIV/AIDS and understand the factors influencing their decisions to seek or avoid such services.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives of the Study:

a) What is the level of awareness and knowledge about HIV/AIDS and VCT among senior high school students?

b) What are the attitudes and perceptions of senior high school students towards VCT services?

c) Which factors and barriers influence the decision-making process regarding the utilization of VCT utilization among senior high school students?

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The research is important because it can help us better understand how high school students view and interact with voluntary counselling and HIV/AIDS testing. Through examining the distinct obstacles and prospects encountered by this population, the study can facilitate the development of focused interventions, well-informed policies, and an all-encompassing strategy for HIV/AIDS prevention and assistance among high school students.

This, in turn, can lead to more engagement in testing and counseling programs, resulting in improved health outcomes. Furthermore, the study can identify specific barriers that impede students from receiving these services. Addressing these limitations is critical to increasing the overall efficacy of HIV/AIDS prevention initiatives. The insights can also help policymakers and stakeholders understand the needs and preferences of this group, resulting in more targeted and effective efforts. In essence, this study has the potential to greatly improve public health by guiding more effective HIV/AIDS interventions among high school students.

1.6 DELIMITATIONS.

This study focused on senior high school students in the Asuogyaman District. It was limited to only those aged 15 to 19 years.

1.7 LIMITATIONS

Due to its heavy reliance on self-reported data, the study is prone to bias. It is possible that students gave answers that were socially acceptable, which caused them to overestimate or underestimate their true views and behaviors about VCT. The study depended on the participants' recollections of prior encounters, understanding, and perspectives which could have introduced errors and compromised the data's trustworthiness.

It is possible that the study undervalued the impact of changing HIV/AIDS awareness campaigns or actions that took place either before or during the research period. Students' viewpoints might have been altered and these outside variables might not have been entirely under control.

1.8 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS

Adolescent: A person who is in the process of developing from a child into an adult. A person aged 10 to 19 years.

Youth: It refers to the period of life between childhood and adulthood. It generally refers to people in their teenage years and early twenties.

Senior High School (SHS): A type of secondary education in Ghana that provides students with a more specialized and practical education.

Voluntary Counselling and Testing: The process by which an individual undergoes professional guidance to enable them to make an informed choice about being tested for HIV.

Perspective: A point of view or a particular attitude towards a subject.

Stigma: A set of negative and unfair beliefs a society or group of people have about a subject.

Awareness: Level of knowledge and understanding about a subject.

Support system: A network of people or resources such as family, peers, and community services which provide emotional and practical support.

Intervention program: A structured and organized plan to address specific issues or challenges faced by an individual.

CHAPTER TWO

2.1 LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF HIV/AIDS AND VCT.

A study (Tagore and Kapoor, 2017) of the knowledge on reproductive health amongst Indian adolescents found gaps in knowledge on the legally required minimum age for marriage, contraceptive methods, and STIs/AIDS. The findings revealed major gaps in students' awareness, notably regarding reproductive health issues. The study discovered that for all participants, understanding of HIV/AIDS recorded 65.4%, knowledge about adverse effects scored 57.5%, knowledge concerning safeguarding scored 59.9%, knowledge about therapy scored 66.8%, understanding about the cause scored 48.5%, and understanding about medico-legal aspects scored 39.1%.

It also indicated that education, communication, and information-sharing strategies are required to increase schoolchildren's understanding of reproductive health issues as well as gender-related concerns. Furthermore, the study emphasized the significance of performing sociocultural research to find acceptable sexual health treatments for adolescent females.

In a study (Lesmana, Ikhsan and Azka, 2021) in South Africa, it was discovered the knowledge level of grade 12 senior high school students at was largely good, having 70.6% demonstrating good understanding on HIV/AIDS. The research discusses how gender and a knowledge source influence students' awareness about HIV/AIDS. The study found that women have higher levels of awareness about HIV/AIDS than males, and the origin of information has a direct impact on knowledge.(Lesmana, Ikhsan and Azka, 2021) It recognizes the internet as a particularly

extensively used source of knowledge about HIV/AIDS for students, highlighting the necessity to leverage online platforms for instructional reasons as information is essential for raising knowledge about HIV/AIDS.(Lesmana, Ikhsan and Azka, 2021)

According to (Akello, Ogendi and Asweto, 2023) on a study in Kenya, most (64%) of secondary school pupils in reported moderate to high awareness about HIV and AIDS, as well as positive attitudes regarding HIV and AIDS (61.1%). Nevertheless, 15% to 25% of students reported participating in unsafe sexual behavior (Akello, Ogendi and Asweto, 2023). Students with higher to intermediate knowledge engaged in less risky sexual activities, showing a link between knowledge and safer sexual conduct. Those with a negative perspective concerning HIV and AIDS were four times more inclined to indulge in high-risk sexual activities (Akello, Ogendi and Asweto, 2023).

According to a study by (Tungu *et al.*, 2022), age, gender, and class level all have an impact on general understanding about HIV/AIDS, its signs and symptoms, and risk factors as well. The knowledge of HIV/AIDS symptoms, risk factors, and general information was found to be influenced by age, gender, and educational level (Tungu *et al.*, 2022). Age was inversely related with knowledge, implying that younger students had less information regarding HIV/AIDS. Students in form four had a higher level of general knowledge about HIV/AIDS than students in form three (Tungu *et al.*, 2022). This demonstrates that increasing the grade of classes has a significant impact on increasing knowledge about HIV/AIDS. It emphasizes the necessity for ongoing HIV education for students of any gender or age in order to improve their knowledge and comprehension of the disease (Tungu *et al.*, 2022).

A study in Nigeria (Idowu *et al.*, 2023) discovered that the majority (75.6%) of respondents had heard about HIV, showing an adequate level of knowledge among students in high school in Osun, Nigeria. Notwithstanding such a high knowledge rate, just 57.6% of respondents had thorough knowledge of HIV, indicating that there are gaps in their awareness of the infection.

Another study (Idoko, 2022) reveals that although high school pupils in Kaduna Metropolis are aware and knowledgeable about HIV/AIDS, it also identifies problems such as difficulties with terminology, a lack of review channels, and insufficient sex education that limit students' ability to learn more about HIV/AIDS. The study (Idoko, 2022) advises raising HIV/AIDS awareness and sexual education among high school pupils in Kaduna State as to assist them in making informed sexual decisions.

A study by (Anaba, Buabeng and Okai, 2022) showed majority of participants (60%) were ignorant of VHCT, and a sizable proportion (8 in 10) had no knowledge of any VHCT centers.

Despite this lack of awareness, the majority of participants understood the significance of VHCT (70%) and stated a willingness to test for HIV if it were offered in schools (Anaba, Buabeng and Okai, 2022).

Knowledge that parental agreement was not necessary for VHCT, as well as willingness to test in youth-friendly clinics, were associated with increased HIV testing rates.

According to the survey, young people in Tema seldom use VHCT services and have little knowledge of them. (Anaba, Buabeng and Okai, 2022)

A study by (Ofori, Nyarney and Eshun, 2022) showed that the majority of senior high school pupils in Ghana's Lower Manya Krobo Municipality (LMKM) are well-informed about

HIV/AIDS. Students learn from a variety of available sources within their domain. However, despite their extensive awareness, it was discovered that education on HIV/AIDS has no substantial impact on their sexual conduct. This implies that, while students are aware of HIV/AIDS, this awareness does not always translate into behavior change. The study (Ofori, Nyarne and Eshun, 2022) underlines the need for intensive sex education to raise HIV/AIDS awareness among students and community members in LMKM.

2.2 ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS VCT SERVICES.

Roughly half of respondents in a study by (Fuster-RuizdeApodaca *et al.*, 2017) believed they had a lower risk of HIV infection than the overall population. A little more than 40% ascribed their low risk perception to the assumption that AIDS affects only certain groups of people. Despite this, more than 90% acknowledged a significant risk of HIV transmission if condoms were not worn during sexual intercourse (Fuster-RuizdeApodaca *et al.*, 2017). The results obtained demonstrate a complicated interaction of risk perception among respondents. While a sizable proportion believed they were less vulnerable to HIV, their reasoning was frequently based on misconceptions about the disease's impact on specific populations and as such unlikely to get tested. However, the widespread recognition of the significant risk associated with unprotected sexual activity suggests a level of understanding about the significance of condoms in preventing HIV transmission (Fuster-RuizdeApodaca *et al.*, 2017).

The study emphasizes the necessity of addressing common misconceptions and improving people's risk perception. Efforts should be directed on dispelling myths about HIV/AIDS, particularly those relating to the perceived groups impacted by the disease. Furthermore,

supporting consistent condom usage is critical, as respondents' understanding of its usefulness in preventing HIV transmission suggests a possible channel for focused education and prevention initiatives.

A study by (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021) showed that 24% of the individuals reported having previously undergone HIV testing. The study (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021) discovered that the intention to test for HIV was substantially associated with various characteristics. There was a positive correlation between subjective norm to test, intention to use condoms, intention to reduce alcohol consumption, subjective norm to reduce alcohol use, and subjective norm to use condoms (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021). Further investigation (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021) found that attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control explained 43% of the variation in intention to test for HIV. Notably, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control each contributed significantly to this variance (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021). Participants' intention to limit alcohol and drug use, as well as their intention to use condoms, accounted for an additional 12% of the variance in HIV testing intentions (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021).

The findings (Manyaapelo *et al.*, 2021) indicate that initiatives aimed at increasing HIV testing among men should target normative and control beliefs. Addressing other risky behaviors, such as alcohol consumption and irregular condom usage, may also increase motivation to get tested for HIV. By addressing these issues, behavioral treatments have the potential to boost HIV testing rates.

In a study by (Katirayi *et al.*, 2021), it was discovered that adolescents living with HIV reported that communications geared at their demographic tend to highlight the importance of staying

HIV-negative rather than the benefits and empowerment that come with knowing one's HIV-positive status. They cited a perceived lack of encouragement or information on the importance of early detection, access to treatment, and support services for PLHIV (Katirayi *et al.*, 2021). This messaging disparity reflects a wasted chance to educate and empower HIV-positive teenagers about their disease, which could lead to delayed diagnosis and treatment. Efforts to change the narrative by destigmatizing HIV and encouraging proactive healthcare seeking behaviors among HIV-positive youth could significantly enhance outcomes and quality of life.

In a study by (Maduakolam *et al.*, 2020), respondents had a good attitude about the utilization of Voluntary Counselling and Testing (VCT) services. Male and female pupils had no significant differences in their attitudes towards testing. A higher number of respondents said that they used VCT services effectively. The study (Maduakolam *et al.*, 2020), however, found no significant association between attitude and utilization of VCT services. This implies that, while the teenagers in the research had a good attitude about testing, it was not necessarily leading to increased use of VCT services.

In (Mason *et al.*, 2022) several prominent themes emerged in relation to HIV self-testing among Nigerian youth. The study revealed seven unique perceptions that influence HIV self-testing. Positive themes included accessibility to testing, the potential for stigma reduction, and the autonomy it provides to people who want to know their status.

In contrast, the study (Mason *et al.*, 2022) revealed unfavorable variables that influence HIV self-testing uptake. Participants expressed a lack of understanding of the process as well as the ongoing stigma associated with HIV. Furthermore, concerns were voiced concerning the

packaging of the self-testing kits and the ads linked with them, indicating a need for improvement in these areas to boost the acceptance and utilization of HIV self-testing services by Nigerian youth.

A study by (Djan, 2018) showed that counselor attitudes, levels of awareness, perceptions of PLHIV, and socio-demographic parameters like age, sex, education level, and location of inhabitants all influence young people's attitudes regarding HIV testing in Techiman Municipality. The overall incidence of voluntary counselling and testing services for HIV/AIDS was determined to be connected with socio-demographic variables, knowledge of HCT centers, HIV status, and having ever visited an HCT center.

Perception, attitude, and a lack of motivation for testing were important predictors of HCT service use by providers in the Techiman district. Respondents' willingness for HIV testing is driven by their understanding regarding HIV and their personal health state, as well as their visit to the HCT center.

2.3 FACTORS AFFECTING THE USE OF VCT.

In a study by (Leistikow *et al.*, 2022), it was found that screening for HIV involves hurdles that include stigma, fear, and worries regarding confidentiality, which may affect young people's willingness to undergo testing and access to care differently than other age groups. It examined the prevalence of HIV test acceptability and connection to care among adolescents using various healthcare delivery methods. The service delivery modes were hospital emergency rooms (ER), primary healthcare/inpatient setting, community-driven scheme, and a sexually transmitted disease (STD) clinic. The study discovered a considerable disparity in HIV testing acceptance

across healthcare designs, with high rates in the emergency rooms in North America and in primary care/hospital settings around the world. In a comparable fashion connection to care varied by the system of healthcare, with ERs reporting a substantial proportion of links to healthcare for HIV in North America. Further study is required to maximize results for every health care paradigm to tackle the unique issues encountered by adolescents.

A study by (McKinnon and Vandermorris, 2019) shows that higher rates of HIV testing among teenagers in nations with high HIV prevalence are associated with a lower legal age of consent for independent HIV testing and counselling. International treaties emphasize the ethical significance of acknowledging teenagers' developing capacities, which underpins recommendations to reduce the age of consent. Reducing the consent age is thought to be a practical and psychological means of removing obstacles to service usage. This study (McKinnon and Vandermorris, 2019) indicates that reducing the legal age of consent could help remove this obstacle, particularly in nations with more stringent regulations, which can impede teenagers' access to HIV/AIDS services. This shift may result in a greater adoption of HIV testing and counselling, which has been linked to a decline in HIV infection rates with time.

According to the (Kangogo, 2023), 18.8% of sexually experienced high school students had tested for HIV in their lifetime, with females being more likely than males to do so. Female gender, being Black, sexual debut before the age of 13, several sexual partners, and light physical activity were all positively related with HIV testing. In contrast, Hispanics/Latinos and condom users were less likely to have ever had an HIV test (Kangogo, 2023). The study (Kangogo, 2023) indicates that HIV testing is still low among these students, and addressing sexual risk behaviors is critical to increasing testing rates. The findings indicate that efforts to increase HIV testing and

connection to care for sexually experienced high school students should be stepped up, highlighting the necessity of establishing a healthier nation.

In (Strauss, George and Rhodes, 2017), individual preferences regarding HIV testing and service delivery modalities among South African high school students differ depending on demographics, screening history, and sexual behaviors. There is no unique optimal design that meets the individual requirements of all students. A variety of alternatives might be necessary for optimizing coverage. Students in this research favored HIV testing at a testing center on a Saturday, which involved a finger prick test performed by a clinician who also provided individual counseling. Faster testing periods and a financial incentive to pay associated costs were also desired. The most critical elements were determined to be time, location, exam kind, and who conducted the test.

Understanding individual preferences and service features is critical to ensuring an intervention's success. Providing a variety of testing alternatives to high school students may help boost popularity of voluntary counselling and testing of HIV/AIDS.

According to (Strauss, George and Rhodes, 2018) concerns about cost had the greatest impact on the use of voluntary counselling and testing amongst high school students in KwaZulu-Natal. Confidentiality was a major worry among students choosing HCT. Policymakers and service providers must ensure that confidentiality remains preserved. Monetary incentives could help increase the uptake of HCT. Programs focused at eliminating social stigma, enhancing education, and distributing information regarding HCT and HIV are critical for increasing demand as well as changing attitudes in adolescents.

In a survey by (Shedura and Paul, 2022) it was demonstrated that students who are familiar with VCT services have no confidence in post-testing confidentiality, demonstrating a lack of understanding about the importance of confidentiality when using VCT services. According to the report, all respondents stated that confidentiality was not ensured after testing, which could be a significant cause for their hesitancy to use VCT services.

It was discovered in (Mayaki and Moleki, no date) that 59% of the adolescents polled felt knowledgeable about voluntary counseling and testing (VCT) programs, but many were afraid to use them for fear of receiving positive results. The article suggests that HIV education sessions be included in the school curriculum, as well as the construction of testing centers in high schools, to encourage VCT among adolescents.

The study also suggests that there may be a need to improve the distribution of VCT information to kids and to provide adolescent-friendly VCT health services in schools. Setting up centers for testing in high schools is proposed as a means of encouraging VCT among adolescents. The report underlines the importance of increasing the circulation of VCT information to young people and developing appealing to young people VCT health services in schools.

According to (Obiezu-Umeh *et al.*, 2021) young people in Nigeria have clear preferences when it comes to self-testing for HIV; these choices are influenced by things like cost, discreet testing locations, testing methodologies, and post-testing support. These preferences highlight how crucial it is to modify studies and programs to meet the demands of young people in terms of HIV self-testing in order to increase the uptake of HIVST (Obiezu-Umeh *et al.*, 2021). Designing successful interventions requires an understanding of the factors influencing young Nigerians'

preferences for HIV self-testing. Initiatives that address these preferences—like pricing and accessibility—can improve the way that young people are connected to HIV self-testing programs as well as the essential follow-up care and support.

In a study by (Apanga, Akparibo and Awoonor-Williams, 2015) 91% of those polled were familiar with VCT services for HIV/AIDS. 70% of the study respondents had utilized VCT services within the previous 12 months (Apanga, Akparibo and Awoonor-Williams, 2015). Participants with formal education were more likely to use VCT services than those without education. The desire to know one's HIV status, referral by health providers, and the intention to marry were the primary reasons for increased use of VCT services (Apanga, Akparibo and Awoonor-Williams, 2015). A lack of understanding, fear of stigma, and the idea that HIV/AIDS is not curable were among the reasons for underutilization of VCT services (Apanga, Akparibo and Awoonor-Williams, 2015). The study emphasizes the importance of raising awareness and promoting VCT services using HIV/AIDS education initiatives in order to eliminate stigma and improve utilization.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODS

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design, and this allowed for data to be collected at a single point in time from a diverse group of senior high school students. The Asuogyaman District in Ghana's Eastern Region was the site of this descriptive cross-sectional study on the perspectives of senior high school students on voluntary counselling and testing of HIV/AIDS.

3.2 STUDY POPULATION

The study's population consisted of senior high school students aged 15 to 19 from different senior high schools within the Asuogyaman District. The total population of the study area was 115058. (Reference) while those aged 15 to 19 years was 12798.

3.2.1 Inclusion Criteria

First, in order to keep the senior high school demography in mind, students who were aged of 15 to 19 were included. This age group was selected to correspond with the average age range of students in this stage of education.

One important factor in the inclusion criteria was gender representation. In order to capture any potential gender-specific subtleties in opinions on volunteer counselling and HIV/AIDS testing, it was imperative to aim for a fair mix of male and female participants. This strategy sought to

prevent gender bias and guarantee a thorough investigation of attitudes among high school students.

Additionally, the inclusion criterion considered the academic diversity of pupils in their senior year of high school. A range of grade levels and program choices of students were enrolled in order to investigate potential relationships between attitudes towards VCT and educational attainment. This made it possible to investigate in-depth possible relationships between viewpoints on HIV/AIDS testing and academic standing.

3.2.2 Exclusion Criteria

First, age restrictions were put in place to ensure uniformity among the participants in the study. In order to guarantee that the results were applicable to the particular group of senior high school students, individuals who did not fit within the predetermined age range 15-19 years were eliminated.

Another criterion used to narrow down the study sample was non-attendance. Exclusion of students who did not attend senior high school regularly during the study period guaranteed that the participants were actively involved in the learning environment and fairly represented the target demographic.

The last criterion for exclusion was an explicit refusal to participate, provided that the students made their expressions after being fully informed about the goals and objectives of the study. This criterion guaranteed that individuals participating were willing contributors and valued their autonomy.

3.3 PROFILE OF STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in the Asuogyaman District in the Eastern Region of Ghana.

3.3.1 Background

Asuogyaman District is, founded from the former Kaoga District is located in Ghana's Eastern region. Its land size covers 1,507 square kilometers, which is 5.7% of the region's size. The district capital is Atimpoku. The district shares its northern border with Kwahu Afram Plains, Lower Manya Krobo is to the south, Upper Manya Krobo to the West and South Dayi, Ho West and North Tongu are on the eastern border. The Asuogyaman District is located approximately between latitudes $6^{\circ} 34^{\circ}$ N and $6^{\circ} 10^{\circ}$ N and longitudes $0^{\circ} 1^{\circ}$ W and $0^{\circ} 14^{\circ}$ E.

3.3.2 Population

According to the 2021 population and housing census, the district's population was 126,163. This comprises 49% males and 51% females. The growth rate is 2.1%. It accounts for 4% of the region's population and the 12th largest.

3.3.3 Geography

The area has undulating terrain with various highlands and major water bodies: The Volta River and Lake. The area has a bimodal rainfall pattern, and temperatures which average 28°C each year. The vegetation is a combination of savannah, forest, and semi-forest.

3.3.4 Political and Traditional Structures

The district has six sub-districts: Akosombo, Atimpoku, Senchi, Anum/Boso, Adjena/Gyakiti and Akwamufie/Apeguso. Traditional governance is centered on chieftains from the ethnic groups of Akwamu, Anum, and Bososo.

3.3.4 Economy

Farming is the predominant economic activity. The main crops are plantain, cassava and maize. Fishing is also a major activity especially along the Volta Lake. Manufacturing and service operations are focused in Akosombo, which is home to important firms such as Volta River Authority and Akosombo Textiles Limited. The district has the potential for investment in tourism, agriculture, and manufacturing.

3.3.5 Health Services

The district operates 30 health facilities spread over the sub-districts, They include a hospital, mission and private clinics, as well as public health centers. There are also extensive Community-based Health Planning and Services zones.

3.4 SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Two schools in the district were selected in order to sample students on the various situations that could affect students' attitudes towards VCT.

Selecting the participants was the next step in the sample procedure once the schools were determined. The changing nature of high school student populations meant that a variety of pupils in terms of age, gender, academic standing, and socioeconomic status had to be included.

The goal of this diversity was to improve the range and depth of insights discovered during the study.

Prior to interacting with the pupils, authorization from the school administration was obtained and great care was taken to get the pupils' and, when appropriate, their parents' or legal guardians' informed consent. Establishing confidence and willingness among the participants was a critical step in securing their voluntary participation in the study.

After obtaining consent, randomly sampled pupils from each chosen school to determine which particular students would take part in the study. By using randomization, biases were further reduced and the possibility of producing a representative sample that reflected the larger population of high school students was raised.

There was necessity to strike a balance between thoroughness and efficiency during the sampling process. Acquiring a sufficiently big and diverse sample was the aim, keeping in mind the time and resource limitations typical in educational research environments.

In summary, a simple random sampling technique was used for the study on senior high school students' thoughts on VCT for HIV/AIDS. The research attempted to obtain a nuanced picture of students' attitudes about VCT by using random sample approaches. This would ensure that the findings could be meaningful, applicable, and representative of the high school population.

3.4.1 Sampling technique

In an attempt to construct a sample that would reflect the diversity of senior high school students, a simple random sampling method was employed. This was done by numbering the students and

every student with an even number was selected to participate in the study. This sampling method removed bias and improved the findings' applicability to the larger population of senior high school students. The application of this sampling strategy necessitated a careful approach to random selection driven by a dedication to obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the students' opinions towards VCT.

3.4.2 Sampling size determination

In determining the sample size, Yamane's formula for calculating sample sizes was employed.

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where:

Z = standard deviation of 1.96

$$q = 1 - p$$

p = The knowledge level of adolescents about voluntary counselling and testing of HIV/AIDS (Andoh-Robertson and Ofori, 2018)

e = error margin which is assumed to be 5%

At a confidence interval of 95%, the sample size is calculated as follows

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.821 \times 0.179}{0.05^2}$$

$$0.05^2$$

$$n = 225.8$$

To improve the statistical power and significance, the sample size was increased to 250.

3.5 DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

Quantitative data was collected through structured questionnaires. The questionnaires assessed awareness and knowledge of HIV/AIDS and VCT, attitudes and perceptions towards VCT, as well as factors which influenced students' of VCT. The questionnaire was prepared in English and had total of 27 questions.

3.6 DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Quantitative data was obtained from participants through responses from structured questionnaires, all of which were close-ended. Participants were approached in a courteous manner and their informed consent was requested. The participants were assembled in classrooms, informed about the purpose, advantages of the study before agreeing to take part willingly.

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS

Statistics were based on quantitative data that was collected using structured questionnaires. With the use of statistical software, SPSS, descriptive statistics were conducted to identify the distribution and frequency of different attitudes and levels of knowledge among the senior high school student body.

3.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

During the study process, a number of fundamental ethical standards were respected in the effort to comprehend and sort out the complexities of students' attitudes towards VCT.

First and foremost, getting informed consent was crucial. Assent was obtained from the participating students and, if applicable, consents from their parents or legal guardians, prior to any data collection. This made sure that everyone willingly accepted to participate in the study and was aware of the purpose and possible consequences of the research. Furthermore, participants were guaranteed the privacy and anonymity of their answers, which promoted an atmosphere of transparency and confidence.

To address potential selection bias and assure a varied and representative sample, a fair participation was sought by including students from a variety of backgrounds, consideration was also given to variables such as gender and grade level. This methodology sought to improve the findings' generalizability while avoiding the marginalization of certain populations.

The study's ethical integrity was emphasized by its adherence to informed consent, confidentiality, diversity in sampling all of which are key elements of ethical research conduct.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In a study conducted among 250 senior high school students in the Asuogyaman District, all the questionnaires were filled correctly and appropriately. The results from this research are represented with tables and graphs in this chapter.

4.2 DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 4.2 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants.

Table 4.2

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE (YEARS)		
15	24	9.6
16	116	46.4

17	91	36.4
18	13	5.2
19	6	2.4
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0
SEX		
Male	121	48.4
Female	129	51.6
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0
CLASS		
SHS 1	120	48.0
SHS 2	130	52.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0
RELIGION		
Christianity	232	92.8
Islam	14	5.6
Other	4	1.6
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	250	100.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0
ADDRESS		

Urban	179	71.6
Suburban	50	20.0
Rural	21	8.4
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

The mean age of the participants was 16.44 with the youngest age being 15 years and the oldest being 19 years. Most of the participants were females, 51.6%, while the male participants were 48.4%. There were more participants (52.0%) in SHS 2 than in SHS 1 (48.0%). Almost (92.8%) all the participants were Christians. All the participants were single. A great majority (71.6%) of participants live in urban areas, with 20.0% living in suburban areas and 8.4% in rural areas.

4.3 STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF HIV/AIDS

Table 4.3 shows students' knowledge of HIV/AIDS

Table 4.3

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	109	43.6
Agree	107	42.8
Neutral	33	13.2
Disagree	1	0.4
TOTAL	250	100.0

The majority of students (43.6%) strongly agree that they are knowledgeable about HIV/AIDS. Another 42.8% agree they are knowledgeable about HIV/AIDS. Only 13.2% of students express neutrality regarding their knowledge, implying ambivalence or apathy. A very small minority, 0.4%, disagree with the statement that they are knowledgeable about HIV/AIDS. Overall, 86.4% of students are confident in their understanding of HIV/AIDS.

4.4 STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE ON HOW HIV/AIDS IS TRANSMITTED

Table 4.4 shows students' knowledge on how HIV/AIDS is transmitted

Table 4.4

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	147	58.8
Agree	84	33.6
Neutral	17	6.8
Strongly disagree	2	0.8
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

Majority (58.8%) of students strongly agree that they know how HIV/AIDS is transmitted. Another 33.6% agree about knowing HIV/AIDS is transmitted while 6.8% expressed neutrality. Just 0.8% strongly disagree about knowing how HIV/AIDS is transmitted. A total of 92.4% of students believe they know how HIV/AIDS is transmitted.

4.5 STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE ON PREVENTION OF TRANSMISSION OF HIV/AIDS

Table 4.5 shows students' knowledge on prevention of transmission of HIV/AIDS

Table 4.5

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	117	46.8
Agree	106	42.4
Neutral	21	8.4
Disagree	2	0.8
Strongly disagree	4	1.6
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

A significant 46.8% of students strongly agree and another 42.4% agree on knowing about the prevention of transmission of HIV/AIDS. 8.4% of students were neutral. A very small portion 0.8% of students disagree and 1.6% of students strongly disagree about this statement.

4.6 STUDENTS' BELIEF ON THE IMPORTANCE OF GETTING INFORMED ABOUT HIV/AIDS

Table 4.6 shows students' belief on the importance of getting informed about HIV/AIDS

Table 4.6

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	206	82.4
Agree	42	16.8

Neutral	2	0.8
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

Nearly all students believe in the importance of getting informed about HIV/AIDS with 82.4% strongly agreeing and 16.8% agreeing. Just 0.8% of students were neutral of the subject.

4.7 STUDENTS' AWARENESS ON WHERE TO GET HIV TESTING

Table 4.7 shows students' awareness on where to get HIV testing

Table 4.7

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	35	14.0
Agree	47	18.8
Neutral	41	16.4
Disagree	92	36.8
Strongly disagree	35	14.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

14.0% of students strongly agree that they are aware of where to get HIV testing and another 18.8% of students agree as well. 16.4% are neutral on the statement. A significant 36.4% disagree and another 14.0% strongly disagree that they are aware of where to get HIV testing. This shows more than half of the participants lack awareness of centers for testing for HIV.

4.8 STUDENTS WHO HAVE CONSIDERED GETTING TESTED FOR HIV

Table 4.8 shows students who have considered getting tested for HIV

Table 4.8

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	29	11.6
Agree	28	11.2
Neutral	58	23.2
Disagree	84	33.6
Strongly disagree	51	20.4
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

11.6% strongly agree about having considered getting an HIV test and another 11.2% agree. 23.2% are neutral on this position. A significant portion 33.6% disagree and another 20.4% strongly disagree. This shows a small degree of interest for HIV testing.

4.9 STUDENTS WHO HAVE RECEIVED AN HIV TEST

Table 4.9 shows students who have received an HIV test

Table 4.9

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	2	0.8
Agree	6	2.4
Neutral	4	1.6

Disagree	114	45.6
Strongly disagree	124	49.6
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

A small portion of students have received an HIV test with 0.8% strongly agreeing and 2.4% agreeing. 1.6% were neutral. Most students (95.2%), 45.6% agreeing and 49.6% strongly disagreeing about having received an HIV test. This highlights a significant gap in HIV testing among participants.

4.10 STUDENTS WHO ARE AWARE OF LOCAL RESOURCES FOR HIV/AIDS EDUCATION AND SUPPORT.

Table 4.10 shows students who are aware of local resources for HIV/AIDS education and support

Table 4.10

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	35	14.0
Agree	40	16.0
Neutral	60	24.0
Disagree	77	30.8
Strongly disagree	38	15.2
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

30% of participants are aware of resources for education and support for HIV with 14.0% strongly agreeing and another 16.0% agreeing. 24.0% are neutral. Most are unaware with 30.8% disagreeing and 15.2% strongly disagreeing on the subject. This shows a notable gap in awareness of local resources for HIV education and support.

4.11 STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE ON WHERE TO ACCESS INFORMATION ABOUT HIV PREVENTION.

Table 4.11 shows students' knowledge on where to access information about HIV prevention

Table 4.11

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	49	19.6
Agree	79	31.6
Neutral	54	21.6
Disagree	40	16.0
Strongly disagree	28	11.2
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

19.6% strongly agree and another 31.6% agree on knowing where to access information about HIV prevention. 21.6% are neutral on the subject. 16.0% disagree and another 11.2% strongly disagree about knowing where to access information about HIV prevention.

4.12 STUDENTS' AWARENESS OF LOCAL HEALTHCARE FACILITIES THAT OFFER HIV TESTING

Table 4.12 shows students' awareness of local healthcare facilities that offer HIV testing

Table 4.12

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	34	13.6
Agree	43	17.2
Neutral	71	28.4
Disagree	61	24.4
Strongly disagree	41	16.4
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

13.6% strongly agree and 17.2% agree about being aware of local healthcare facilities that offer HIV testing. A significant 28.4% were neutral. 24.4% disagreed and another 16.4% strongly disagreed about being aware of local healthcare facilities that offer HIV testing.

4.13 STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE ON HOW TO CONTACT LOCAL SUPPORT ORGANIZATIONS

Table 4.13 shows students' knowledge on how to contact local support organizations

Table 4.13

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	23	9.2
Agree	28	11.2
Neutral	51	20.4
Disagree	84	33.6
Strongly disagree	64	25.6
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

9.2%, strongly agree and 11.2% agree about knowing how to contact local support organizations. 20.4% are neutral. 33.6% disagree, and 25.6% strongly disagree. This shows that most students lack knowledge on how to contact local support organizations.

4.14 STUDENTS WHO BELIEVE IT IS IMPORTANT FOR ADOLESCENTS TO GET TESTED FOR HIV.

Table 4.14 shows students who believe it is important for adolescents to get tested for HIV

Table 4.14

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	112	44.8
Agree	66	26.4
Neutral	57	22.8
Disagree	9	3.6
Strongly disagree	6	2.4

<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0
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A great portion of students believe it is important for adolescents to get tested for HIV, with 44.8% strongly agreeing and another 26.4% agreeing. 22.8% are neutral. A small portion of students, 3.6% disagree and 2.4% strongly disagree on this subject.

4.15 STUDENTS WHO THINK GETTING TESTED FOR HIV CAN HELP PREVENT ITS SPREAD

Table 4.15 shows students who think getting for HIV can help prevent its spread

Table 4.15

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	111	44.4
Agree	78	31.2
Neutral	36	14.4
Disagree	10	4.0
Strongly disagree	15	6.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

A significant portion of students believe getting tested for HIV can help prevent its spread, with 44.4% who strongly agree and 31.2% who agree. 14.4% of respondents are neutral. 10.0% do not believe in this subject i.e. 4.0% who disagree and 6.0% who strongly disagree.

4.16 STUDENTS WHO BELIEVE THAT KNOWING YOUR HIV STATUS IS EMPOWERING

Table 4.16 shows students who believe that knowing your HIV status is empowering

Table 4.16

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	105	42.0
Agree	57	22.8
Neutral	54	21.6
Disagree	19	7.6
Strongly disagree	15	6.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

42.0% strongly believe knowing your HIV status is empowering and another 22.8% agree. A significant 21.6% is neutral. 7.6% disagree and 6.0% strongly disagree on the subject.

4.17 STUDENTS WHO CONSIDER VCT A WAY TO ACCESS SUPPORT AND COUNSELING

Table 4.17 shows students who consider VCT a way to access support and counselling

Table 4.17

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
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Strongly agree	82	32.8
Agree	75	30.0
Neutral	88	35.2
Disagree	3	1.2
Strongly disagree	2	0.8
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

32.8% strongly agree and 30.0% agree that VCT is a means to access support and counselling. A significant 35.2% are neutral. Just 2.0% do not consider VCT as a means to access support and counselling, with 1.2% who disagree and 0.8% who strongly disagree on the subject.

4.18 FEAR OF STIGMA AND DISCRIMINATION BEING A BARRIER TO GETTING TESTED FOR HIV.

Table 4.18 shows students who believe fear of stigma and discrimination is a barrier to getting tested for HIV

Table 4.18

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	124	49.6
Agree	88	35.2
Neutral	23	9.2
Disagree	10	4.0

Strongly disagree	5	2.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

Most students believe fear of stigma and discrimination is a barrier to getting tested for HIV with 49.6% strongly agreeing and 35.2% agreeing. 9.2% remain neutral. 4.0% disagree and 2.0% strongly disagree.

4.19 LACK OF PRIVACY AT TESTING FACILITIES BEING A BARRIER TO GETTING TESTED FOR HIV.

Table 4.19 shows students who believe lack of privacy at testing facilities is a barrier to getting tested for HIV

Table 4.19

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	59	23.6
Agree	81	32.4
Neutral	84	33.6
Disagree	16	6.4
Strongly disagree	10	4.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

23.6% strongly agree and 32.4% agree that lack of privacy at testing facilities is a barrier to getting tested for HIV. 33.6% are neutral on the subject. 6.4%, disagree and 4.0% strongly disagree.

4.20 CONCERNS ABOUT CONFIDENTIALITY BEING A BARRIER TO GETTING TESTED FOR HIV.

Table 4.20 shows students whose concerns about confidentiality is a barrier to getting tested for HIV

Table 4.20

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	72	28.8
Agree	76	30.4
Neutral	95	38.0
Disagree	2	0.8
Strongly disagree	5	2.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

28.8% strongly agree and another 30.4% agree that concerns about confidentiality are a barrier to getting tested for HIV. Quite a portion of students, 38.0% are neutral. Just 0.8% disagree and 2.0% strongly disagree.

4.21 CONCERNS ABOUT THE COST ASSOCIATED WITH HIV TESTING BEING A BARRIER TO GETTING TESTED FOR HIV.

Table 4.21 students whose concerns about the cost associated with HIV testing being a barrier to getting tested for HIV

Table 4.21

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	23	9.2
Agree	37	14.8
Neutral	93	37.2
Disagree	55	22.0
Strongly disagree	42	16.8
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

9.2% of students strongly agree and 14.8% agree that concerns about cost of HIV testing are a barrier to getting tested for HIV. 37.2% are neutral on this subject. 22.0% disagree and 16.8% strongly disagree.

4.22 STUDENTS BEING ENCOURAGED BY FRIENDS ABOUT KNOWING THEIR HIV STATUS

Table 4.22 shows students who are encouraged by friends about knowing their HIV status

Table 4.22

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	35	14.0
Agree	14	5.6
Neutral	51	20.4
Disagree	85	34.0
Strongly disagree	65	26.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

14.0% strongly agree and 5.6% agree about having been encouraged by friends to know their HIV status. 20.4% are neutral. A great number of students, 34.0%, disagree and 26.0% strongly disagree on the subject.

4.23 STUDENTS WHOSE FAMILIES WERE SUPPORTIVE ABOUT THEM GETTING TESTED FOR HIV

Table 4.23 shows students whose families were supportive about them getting tested for HIV

Table 4.23

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	25	10.0
Agree	25	10.0
Neutral	91	36.4
Disagree	74	29.6

Strongly disagree	35	14.0
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

10.0% strongly agree and 10.0% agree that their families are supportive about them getting tested for HIV. A significant 36.4% are neutral. 29.6% disagree and 14.0% strongly disagree, showing that most students' families were not supportive about them getting tested for HIV.

4.24 DISCUSSION OF HIV BY TEACHERS IN A HELPFUL WAY

Table 4.24 shows students who found discussion of HIV by teachers helpful

Table 4.24

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	83	33.2
Agree	51	20.4
Neutral	51	20.4
Disagree	46	18.4
Strongly disagree	19	7.6
<i>TOTAL</i>	250	100.0

Most students, 33.2% strongly agree and 20.4% agree that teachers discuss HIV in a helpful way.

20.4% are neutral. 18.4% disagree and 7.6% strongly disagree.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This study assessed the level of awareness and knowledge about HIV/AIDS and VCT among senior high school students. The study also looked at the attitudes and perceptions of students towards VCT services, as well as factors and barriers that influence the decision-making process on the utilization of VCT.

5.2 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF PARTICIPANTS

The participants were aged 15 to 19 years with most of them being aged 16 or 17 years. There were more female participants (51.6%) than male participants (48.4%). Since SHS 3 students had graduated, only students from SHS 2 and SHS 1 could be sampled. SHS 2 students formed a majority (52.0%) of the sampled students while SHS 1 students comprised 48.0%. Almost (92.8%) all the participants were Christians, given that Christianity predominates in the district. 5.6% of participants were Muslims and 1.6% belong to other faith. All the participants were single. A great majority (71.6%) of participants live in urban areas, with 20.0% living in suburban areas and 8.4% in rural areas.

5.3 LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF HIV/AIDS AND VCT

Most of the students (86.4%) feel knowledgeable about HIV/AIDS, indicating a high level of confidence. This finding has been confirmed by a study (Lesmana, Ikhsan and Azka, 2021). There is a 13.2% neutrality and a negligible 0.4% who disagreed indicates that students have a basic understanding of what HIV/AIDS is. This could be attributed to HIV awareness and education campaigns, as well as its inclusion in the school curriculum.

A significant majority (92.4%) of students feel knowledgeable about transmission of HIV/AIDS. It can be inferred from this knowledge about transmission of HIV is soundly established and this is necessary for prevention strategies. The few neutrals (6.8%) and those who strongly disagree (0.8%) shows there is little misconception about the transmission of HIV among them. Most of the students agree about knowing about prevention of transmission of HIV. It points out there is great awareness on preventive strategies which is necessary in decreasing transmission rates.

However, continuous education is necessary to reinforce this knowledge to ensure preventive strategies are applied properly.

Almost all participants (99.2%) believe in the importance of getting informed about HIV/AIDS. This highlights the role knowledge about HIV plays in the prevention, as well as supports policies on HIV education programs.

Students' awareness on testing centers for HIV, with just about a third of students knowing of such centers. This is similar to findings by (Anaba, Buabeng and Okai, 2022) This lack of awareness is a hindrance to VCT since students may not get tested if they are unaware of such centers. Measures should be put in place to increase the visibility and accessibility of test centers in order to improve testing rates.

There is a low degree of voluntary testing of HIV with just 22.8% students having considered ever getting tested and just 3.2% who have actually received an HIV test. This could be attributed to factors like fear of stigma and discrimination associated with positive results. It could also signify that knowledge and awareness of HIV has not been well translated to action by getting tested. It is important that benefits of VCT be promoted and barriers like stigma and unawareness of testing centers should be addressed.

Although the participants had a good knowledge base about HIV/AIDS, there was a low level of awareness and use of VCT. This is confirmed by (Anaba, Buabeng and Okai, 2022).

5.4 ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS VCT SERVICES

Generally, there was positive attitude towards VCT. More than two-thirds of the participants believe in the importance of adolescents getting tested for HIV/AIDS. This reflects a positive attitude by students towards VCT as a preventive measure. In order to further strengthen these attitudes, awareness campaigns should address misconceptions and promote the benefits of VCT.

Most students also believe that getting tested for HIV can help prevent its spread. This suggests that most students are aware of the importance of VCT in stopping the spread of HIV, which is essential for public health interventions.

There is a positive perception of the benefits of VCT with 64.8% who believe knowing one's HIV status is empowering. This is consistent with findings from (Mason *et al.*, 2022). A few students disagreeing suggests some students do not realize the role of VCT and as such, efforts should be made to highlight the benefits of knowing one's status, such as having access to treatment and preventing its spread.

Most students also believe in VCT being a means to access support and counselling. This is significant as it shows the recognition of the wider advantages VCT offers, which goes beyond testing.

5.5 FACTORS AFFECTING THE USE OF VCT

Most participants (at least eight out of every ten participant) feel fear of stigma and discrimination is a barrier to getting tested. This high number indicates that the general perception of taking an HIV test is laden with fear of stigma and has prevented them from getting tested. This is consistent with findings by (Leistikow *et al.*, 2022).

Most respondents either strongly agreed or agreed that a lack of privacy at testing centers is a barrier to getting tested for HIV. The significance of privacy demonstrates how most people live in fear of their test results being disclosed to others. This finding agrees with (Shedura and Paul, 2022) where participants did not have confidence in privacy and confidentiality at testing centers.

Compared to other factors, concerns about cost seems to have little significance with 24% of participants finding it concerning. On the other hand, 38.8% of students disagree or strongly disagree about cost being a barrier to HIV testing. With 37.2% neutral responses, this could suggest that while cost might be a barrier to some individuals, it is not a universal barrier to getting tested.

Most responses revealed that there is little to no encouragement from friends or family to get tested. The lack of peer support suggests that HIV and VCT may not be a common topic of discussion among participants and their friends. Although, families and friends may not be encouraging respondents to get tested, it does not necessarily they are being discouraged, but possible are doing little to nothing to foster VCT.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to shed light on the perspectives of senior high school students regarding VCT of HIV, which will contribute to the development of effective interventions to promote the VCT utilization among this vulnerable population. The results could be used to advocate for evidence-

based policies and initiatives to improve HIV/AIDS awareness and prevention in senior high schools.

This study supports a number of previous studies showing that senior high school students are generally aware of HIV/AIDS. * through VCT, with an almost negligible number of students who have been tested. This suggests a mismatch between knowledge and action which may be due to fear of stigma and discrimination, lack of encouragement from peers. There is the need for more robust campaigns to education and awareness on VCT.

Results from this study also indicate that there is a strong recognition of the importance of HIV testing among students with most of them acknowledging its role in preventing transmission. However, there are still significant gaps in the levels of knowledge and awareness of VCT, which should be addressed. Most students believe being aware of their HIV status is empowering and they consider VCT an important resource to accessing support and counselling. These positive perceptions emphasize the potential advantages of VCT programs in determining HIV status, as well as providing psychological and social support.

Despite these positive perceptions, the study identifies significant barriers to the use of VCT. A large majority of students recognize the fear of stigma and discrimination to being a hindrance to getting tested. Also, most students are concerned about privacy and confidentiality at test centers, which suggests that improvements that aspect would motivate more students to get tested. For most students, cost does not seem to be a barrier to getting tested but a lack of awareness of where to get tested seems to be the issue. This lack of awareness further extends to local resources for HIV education and support, and has hindered students from getting tested. Support

from friends and family for HIV testing is significantly low and has translated to low levels of testing.

This suggests that comprehensive strategies are required to reduce stigma and discrimination associated with positive results, improve the visibility of test centers and create a more supportive environment through community and family engagement programs. Through these strategies, the overall effectiveness of VCT in HIV prevention can be improved among students.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Enhanced awareness campaigns on VCT. In order to bridge the gap between knowledge and action, comprehensive HIV awareness campaigns with emphasis on VCT should be launched. These campaigns should incorporate detailed information on the importance of VCT in HIV prevention, testing centers and how to access them, as well as demystify misconceptions about testing. Various media outlets like social media, television and radio will be useful in order to reach a wider audience.
2. Improve visibility and accessibility of test centers. This should involve providing detailed information and location of test centers, how to access them and operating hours. Collaborations could also be made with organizations to provide mobile testing services to schools to make testing easier.
3. Community and family engagement programs. In order to foster a supportive environment for VCT, peers and family should be engaged. Peer-led initiatives will encourage HIV testing and provide support to those contemplating it. Also, testimonials from peers who have been tested will help address the fear of stigma associated with

testing. Providing families with resources and training to freely discuss HIV and VCT will contribute to a more supportive environment at home and reduce stigma and discrimination.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE

Title: The Perspective of Voluntary Counselling and Testing for HIV/AIDS in some Senior High Schools in the Asuogyaman District.

I am Fitzgerald Adjierteh Adjetey, a final year medical student of the KNUST School of Medicine and Dentistry, conducting a study on the above topic. Participation is voluntary and you may opt out at any time if you wish to do so. It would be appreciated if you provide honest answers to these questions. This is purely for academic purposes and any information provided is completely anonymous and confidentiality is assured.

Thank you for your participation.

Section 1: Demographics

Age

Sex

- Male
- Female

Grade level

- SHS 1
- SHS 2
- SHS 3

Religion

- Christianity
- Islam
- African Traditional Religion
- Other

Marital Status

- Single
- Married
- Divorced
- Separated

In which area do you live?

- Urban
- Suburban
- Rural

Please answer subsequent questions based of the following scale: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree.

Section 2: Level of awareness and knowledge about HIV/AIDS and VCT among senior high school students.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I have a good understanding of what HIV is.					
I know how HIV is transmitted.					

I am aware of the ways to prevent HIV transmission.					
I believe it is important to be informed about HIV.					
I am aware of where to get HIV testing in my community.					
I have considered getting an HIV test.					
I have previously received an HIV test.					
I am aware of local resources for HIV/AIDS education and support.					
I know where to access information about HIV prevention.					
I am aware of local					

healthcare facilities that offer HIV testing.					
I know how to contact local support organizations.					

Section 3: Attitudes and perceptions of senior high school students towards VCT services.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I believe it's important for adolescents to get tested for HIV.					
I think getting tested for HIV can help prevent its spread.					
I believe that					

knowing your HIV status is empowering.					
I consider VCT a way to access support and counseling.					

Section 4: Factors that influence the decision making process regarding the utilization of VCT services among senior high school students.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Fear of stigma and discrimination is a barrier to getting tested for HIV.					
Lack of privacy at					

testing facilities deters me from testing.					
I'm concerned about confidentiality when getting tested.					
I worry about the cost associated with HIV testing.					
My friends encourage me to know my HIV status.					
My family is supportive of getting tested for HIV.					

My teachers discuss HIV/AIDS in a helpful way.					
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LETTER OF INTRODUCTION

DCH/DO/06001

September 28, 2023

The Medical Superintendent

Volta River Authority Hospital

Akosombo

Dear Sir,

REQUEST FOR ATTACHMENT OF 5TH YEAR MEDICAL STUDENTS FOR FIELD/DISTRICT ROTATIONS

I write to introduce you to Adjetey Fitzgerald Adjierteh, who is a fifth-year medical student in the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology School of Medicine and Dentistry. As part of the training offered by the Department of Community Health of the School, fifth year medical students are required to undertake a five-week field/district posting. Within this period, the students are expected to actively engage with the health delivery system by carrying out the following:

1. Clinical observation and experience in the health facility
2. Public health activities with the District Health Management Team
3. Collecting data for their thesis (not necessarily at the same location)

The students will carry out the required field/district postings and data collection from October 30 to December 01, 2023, following which they will return to school to begin their final year.

The Department would like to kindly request for your permission to have the student attached to your facility/organization in order to carry out their field/district posting. Any additional support that you can provide to the student to facilitate their attachment would be greatly appreciated and duly recognized. While on attachment, the student will be subject to the rules and regulations governing your facility/organization.

Attached to this letter is a form aimed at verifying the field/district posting. This form includes key activities the students are to be engaged in over the period. Students are expected to perform at least 85% of the listed activities. Either you or an authorized representative of the facility/organization is kindly requested to countersign and stamp the form at the end of the attachment period.

I am hopeful that with your support, the student will be able to fulfill the requirement of a field/district posting within the stipulated time frame.

Yours truly,

Yeetey Enuameh MD, MSc, DrPH, FWACP

HEAD OF DEPARTMENT

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PROFILE OF STUDY AREA

ASUOGYAMAN DISTRICT PROFILE

Background

Asuogyaman District is one of the thirty-two districts in the Eastern region of Ghana. Until its creation in 1988, the area formed part of the former Kaoga District Council whose capital was Somanya. It covers a total estimated surface area of 1,507 square kilometers and constitutes 5.7% of the total area of eastern region with its capital being Atimpoku.

The District is bordered to the North by the Afram Plains District to the South by North Tongu District West by Manya Krobo District, to the East by South Dai District.

Physical features

The topography of the District is generally undulating, with the following highlands – Tatabum, Krobo Kyei, Bulu, Adomi and Kpegyei. The main water bodies include the Volta River and Lake, River Adobo, River Opotoku, the Baware, Anyinase River and the Bubuakan. Indeed, it is on account of the fact the major settlements are located on either side of the Volta Lake that the name Asuogyaman was adopted for the District (“Asuogya” – Water and “man” – state).

The mean annual rainfall is about 1130mm with a bimodal distribution and a maximum daily amount of about 67mm. The period May-June constitutes the major wet season, with the minor wet season occurring during the period September-November. Annual temperature is about 28°C with average maximum and minimum being 37°C and 19°C respectively. The vegetation of the District is a mixture of Forest, Semi-Forest/Re-growth and Savannah.

Political and Administrative Structure

The political administrative structure is made of district administration and local government structures, namely district assemblies and chieftaincies. Asuogyaman District is one of the twenty seven districts in the Eastern region of Ghana. Until its creation in 1988, the area forms part of the former Kaoga District Council whose capital was Somanya. It covers a total estimated surface area of 1,507 square kilometers and constitutes 5.7% of the total area of eastern region with its capital Atimpoku. There are six sub-districts in the district.

Traditional Administration

Traditional Administration in Asuogyaman District is centered on chieftaincy as practiced by its constituent ethnic groups – Akwamus, Anums and Bosos. Thus the District has three Traditional Councils; each of the ethnic groups has a hierarchy of chiefs headed by a paramount chief followed by divisional chiefs, and village chiefs. The presence of significant Krobo and Ewe settler groups makes the District greatly heterogeneous

Economy and living conditions

Farming constitutes the main economic activity of the majority of the people, with maize, cassava, and plantain being the major crops. Fishing is also done mostly by the Battors. Banana is grown for export as well as exotic vegetables (e.g. green pepper). These ventures (banana and vegetables) are undertaken by private companies. Manufacturing, commercial and service activities are also carried out mostly in Akosombo, with the Akosombo Textiles Limited, Volta Hotel, and Volta River Authority and Volta Lake Transport Company Limited are the main operatives. Akosombo also houses the most viable market in the District. The district now has one of the finest and luxuries hotel know as Royal Senchi.

The Asuogyaman District has vast potentials for investment particularly, in the area of tourism, agriculture and industry.

There are also fish farming along the lake in areas like Marine, Kudi Kope, Asikuma, Sedorm, and Atimpoku in the district. Asikuma also holds the largest fish market in the district, with people coming from both within and outside the district to patronize their services. There is also a Chain Saw Operators in Sedorm called Sustainable development that is specialized cutting of trees in the Lake for both local and international use.

HEALTH SERVICES

The district has to a total of Thirty (30) health facilities in six sub-districts. The break done of the health facilities is as follows:

- Health Centers (Public)

- 10

- Hospital (Volta River Authority) - 1
- Health Centre (CHAG, Salvation Army) - 1
- Private Clinic/HC - 3
- CHPS - 45 demarcated zones
 - Functional - 35
 - CHPS with Compound - 13
 - CHPS with Rented or Borrowed compound - 3
 - CHPS without compound - 3
 - CHPS in Health centers - 11

Health Facilities by Ownership

TYPE OF FACILITY	NUMBER	OWNERSHIP
Hospital	1	VRA
Public Health Centers	10	Ghana Health Service
Mission clinic	1	Salvation Army
Private clinics	3	Hedwig's clinic, NAAB's clinic, and Destiny
Outreach centers	94	Ghana health Service
CHPS	35 functional	Ghana health Service

The Health Structure

The Asuogyaman District, with about 122 communities is divided into 6 sub-districts namely:

- Akosombo
- Atimpoku
- Senchi
- Akwamufie-Apeguso
- Anum-Boso and
- Adjena-Gyakiti.

The Asuogyaman District Health System is based on a 3-tier Primary Health Care.

- The district
- The sub-district and
- The Community Based Health Planning and Services (CHPS) at the

community level.

Health Services Facilities in the Asuogyaman District, 2022

S/N	Sub-District	H F	CHPS	Eye Clinic	Health Centre	Hospital	Dental
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1	Atimpoku	5	4	0	1	0	0
2	Senchi	5	5	1	3	0	1
3	Akosombo	3	7	0	1	1	0
4	Akwamufie / Apeguso	7	7	0	4	0	0
5	Anum/ Boso	5	7	0	2	0	0
6	Adjena/ Gyakiti	5	6	0	1	0	0
7	Asuogyaman	30	36	1	12	1	1

Demographics

The population of the district is 126163 for 2021 and is made up of 49% males and 51% females (Ghana Statistics, Census, 2010). The district population constitutes 4 percent of the regional population and the 12th largest populated district in the region.

Projected Population, Asuogyaman

SUB-DISTRICTS	2020	2021	2022 Census
Asuogyaman(Growth rate = 2.1)	123043	126163	103382
AKOSOMBO	24500	13508	11069
ATIMPOKU	14476	16091	13186
SENCHI	18099	16041	13144
ANUM/BOSO	23998	28158	23073
AKWAMUFIE/APEGUSO	27039	32236	26416
ADJENA/GYAKITI	14931	20129	16494

Mission

To provide quality health service responsive to the needs of all persons living in Asuogyaman by implementing approved health sector policies, increase access to priority health services and manage prudently resources available for provision of health services

Vision

The vision of the Asuogyaman is to improve health status and reduced inequalities in health outcomes of all people living in the district.

To improve the health status of all people living in Asuogyaman that:

- ✓ All children shall survive beyond five years
- ✓ All Pregnant women shall have safe delivery and healthy babies
- ✓ All people shall be educated to live healthy life style and avoid Communicable and Non-communicable diseases

Core values

- Partner friendly
- Professionalism
- Teamwork
- Innovation/Excellence
- Evidence Based Decision

